

ENHANCED WIRELESS NETWORK SECURITY AND EFFICIENCY BASED ON RADIO FINGERPRINT FREQUENCY USING MACHINE LEARNING TECHNIQUES

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ABSTRACT

In today's connected world, almost everyone has at least one internet-connected device. With the number of these devices on the rise, it is important to implement a security strategy to minimize their potential for exploitation. Internet-connected devices may be used by nefarious entities to collect personal information, steal identities, and compromise financial data. we use Machine Learning techniques. Radio Frequency (RF) fingerprinting is a technique that allows the identification of radio transmitters by analyzing the spectrum of their transmissions. Small imperfections in the electromagnetic emissions of radio transmitters make it possible to identify them based only on the way they transmit.

This is called Radio Frequency (RF) fingerprinting. Indeed a device's spectrum is unique because of tiny imperfections in the manufacturing process of its analog components. Analyzing a device's spectrum can typically be done using machine learning

algorithms. It will give more accuracy compared to the previous system.

Keywords : RF, Fingerprint, WSN, Security.

1. INTRODUCTION

Just like we each have unique fingerprints, radio transmitters also have different radio frequency fingerprints, namely, RF fingerprints. The RF fingerprints come from differences between hardware components of transmitters, and the differences can be reflected in communication signals. The fingerprints can be extracted by processing transient signal or steady-state signal from received RF signals. The method to obtain transmitter hardware characteristics is called RF fingerprint extraction, and the method to identify individual transmitter with fingerprints is called RF fingerprint identification. The RF fingerprints work in physical layer within transmission devices, so they cannot be destroyed or copied.

RF fingerprint is a popular area of research in recent decades, and it is widely

applied in spectrum resource management, wireless equipment safety certification, the mobile phone network protection, and other fields. The fractal dimensions (box dimension and information dimension) were extracted as RF fingerprints to identify 3 FM stations. Three fingerprint extraction algorithms based on the Hilbert spectrum were introduced. RF fingerprints based on dual-tree complex wavelet transform (DT-CWT) features were extracted from the no transient preamble response of OFDM-based 802.11a signals.

In this paper, the inherent nonlinearities of radio transmitters are analysed, and they can be extracted as RF fingerprints of the signals. As a result, a new RF fingerprinting method based on multidimension permutation entropy is proposed. We design a signal acquisition system to collect signals, and the DSSS signals from the same three radio transmitters are used in identification experiments. The results show that the proposed method is effective in differentiating individual transmitters.

2. LITERATURE SURVEY

[1] The nearest neighbour's decision rule assigns to an unclassified sample point the classification of the nearest of a set of previously classified points. This rule is independent of the underlying joint distribution on the sample points and their classifications, and hence the probability of error R of such a rule must be at least as great as the Bayes

probability of error R^{\ast} --the minimum probability of error over all decision rules taking underlying probability structure into account. However, in a large sample analysis, we will show in the M -category case that $R^{\ast} \leq R \leq R^{\ast}(2 - MR^{\ast}/(M-1))$, where these bounds are the tightest possible, for all suitably smooth underlying distributions. Thus, for any number of categories, the probability of error of the nearest neighbour's rule is bounded above by twice the Bayes probability of error. In this sense, it may be said that half the classification information in an infinite sample set is contained in the nearest neighbour.

[2] Feature based camera model identification plays an important role for forensics investigations on images. The conventional feature-based identification schemes suffer from the problem of unknown models, that is, some images are captured by the camera models previously unknown to the identification system. To address this problem, we propose a new scheme: Source Camera Identification with Unknown models (SCIU). It has the capability of identifying images of the unknown models as well as distinguishing images of the known models. The new SCIU scheme consists of three stages: 1) unknown detection; 2) unknown expansion; and 3) $(K+1)$ -class classification. Unknown detection applies a k -nearest neighbours' method to recognize a few sample images of unknown

models from the unlabelled images. Unknown expansion further extends the set of unknown sample images using a self-training strategy. Then, we address a specific (K+1)-class classification, in which the sample images of unknown (1-class) and known models (K-class) are combined to train a classifier. In addition, we develop a parameter optimization method for unknown detection, and investigate the stopping criterion for unknown expansion. The experiments carried out on the Dresden image collection confirm the effectiveness of the proposed SCIU scheme. When unknown models present, the identification accuracy of SCIU is significantly better than the four state-of-art methods: 1) multi-class Support Vector Machine (SVM); 2) binary SVM; 3) combined classification framework; and 4) decision boundary carving.

[3] Radio frequency signal identification technology is a non-password authentication method based on the physical layer hardware of the device. This paper explores the feature extraction and recognition method based on the gene characteristics of the radio frequency signal. Since the radio frequency signal has materiality, informationally, transitivity, vulnerability and dividability, these characters are similar to biological gene. The concept of gene characteristics of the radio frequency signal is proposed in the paper, which is inspired by the biological gene. The study on radio frequency signal gene characteristics from

the perspective of fractal theory based on the self-similarity of the radio frequency signal is carried out, and the radio frequency signal gene feature extraction is explored by the multifractal dimension characteristics. The experimental results illustrate that the recognition success rate of 500 sets of radio frequency signals from ten identical radio stations can reach 98.2% with the gray relation algorithm as a classifier. It shows that the multifractal dimension characteristics can be used to express the gene features of the radio frequency signals, although the time domain signals from these ten identical radio stations are basically similar. Extending to the cognitive research of radio frequency signals, it can be applied to enhance physical layer security for industrial Internet of Things (IoT) through collaborative identity authentication of industrial IoT wireless devices based on the radio frequency signal gene characteristics.

3. PROPOSED METHODOLOGY

- Analyzing a device's spectrum can typically be done using machine learning algorithms.
- RFFID method refers to identification based on the radio frequency signal fingerprint of the wireless devices to confirm the access of the legal wireless devices, thereby realizing the identity authentication of the wireless devices.

- It will give more accuracy compared to the previous system.
- Here we proposed the supervised machine learning algorithms.
- In Supervised used SVM, Random forest, Decision Tree and Regression algorithms.
- Proposed system secure WSN use of Radio finger printing techniques.
- Real time data used.
- Preprocessing and analyzing data is easy.

4. SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE

System architecture is the conceptual model that defines the structure, behaviour, and more views of a system. An architecture description is a formal description and representation of a system, organized in a way that supports reasoning about the structures and behaviours of the system.

5. SYSTEM MODULE

Incorporating Finite Impulse Response Filters in Deep Learning. In this section, we discuss our implementation of FIR filters in our Baseline model for improved classification accuracy. FIR filters are advantageous in the setting of neural networks because (1) they do not require feedbacks, (2) they inherit stability and introduce robustness, and (3) FIR weights can be trained in a deep learning setting. With this in hand, we first introduce FIR filters to enhance inherent features in transmission signals. Second, we estimate channel conditions with FIR filters through an approximate deconvolution.

6. RESULT AND DISCUSSIONS

7. CONCLUSION

In this thesis, we discuss applications of deep learning to problems in radio fingerprinting. Traditionally, radio fingerprinting consisted of crafting protocol specific features from wireless device transmissions. Such features would be hand picked from characteristics such as: the clock jitter, I/Q signal offsets, or signal power. This process used to be manually-intensive, slow, and always left room for devices to be unidentifiable. With the success of deep learning in image processing, speech recognition and natural language processing, deep learning has recently been introduced to radio fingerprinting. Through neural networks, features that characterize wireless devices are extracted automatically when learning the model parameters. In addition to this, neural networks are protocol independent which allows for generality in the learned parameters. We use deep learning in two contexts of radio fingerprinting: (1) building MAC ID spoof-resistant radio fingerprinting classifiers, and (2) introducing FIR filters to neural networks. In the work of MAC ID spoofing-resistant radio

fingerprinting we analyze that Baseline model's classification of wireless transmissions is not dependent on an identifier sequence included in the signal. If the classification was taking into consideration the MAC ID as an important feature, the model itself would be meaningless. To prove the Baseline is doing the contrary, we show trained classifiers to not improve in accuracy drastically after including the MAC ID. We show this through an ADS-B sub-dataset, and we additionally verify the classifier's resistance to MAC ID spoofing through a sub-dataset with scrambled MAC IDs and a Bitwise identical sub-dataset. Future work could use adversarial learning to increase resistance against MAC ID spoofing under different.

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